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Water Management and its Conservation in Ancient India

Dr. Pratyancha Pandey*

One of the things which make this planet a distinctive planet in this universe is continuous availability of water, a vital thing for existence of life. Water had been considered as life in Ancient Indian culture. A very large emphasis is given to source of water, importance of water for all living organisms, quality and its usefulness. According to Ancient Indian Civilization, each and every type of water present in this universe should be conserved by us. All the ancient civilization known to history and archeology thrived on the banks of rivers. Water is also the essential prerequisite of agriculture, the source of food needed for the survival of life as without it there can hardly be any civilization. So, the proper management of water and its conservation is very important. The proper management of water, its conservation and preservation was also sanctified by the religion. This article seeks to survey and explore the proper management of water and its conservation in ancient India.

So far as our knowledge goes, one of the things which make this globe a distinctive planet in the universe is continuous availability of water, a vital prerequisite for existence of life. Ever since man appeared on the surface of the earth he must have understood the importance of water as is apparent from the fact that all the ancient civilizations known to history and archaeology thrived on the banks of rivers such as Sindhu, Saraswati, Nile, Tigris and Euphrates. Water is essential for agriculture, the source of food needed for the survival of life as without it there can hardly be any cultivation. Thus, life on earth is wholly and solely dependent on water.

The Indus valley civilization from around 3000-1500 B.C. well known as the Harappan civilization, stands one of the earliest and most sophisticated civilizations. The people of Indus Valley civilization were particularly devoted to water, with a daily practice of praying to rivers and attributing divine significance to them. In ancient Indian culture, water always held profound significance, considered as Divine by the ancient scriptures and known as Aap in Sanskrit, is considered to be as old as universe. Harappans were aware about the importance of water. They worship rivers, Varuna and Indra. Varuna was the god of water and Indra was the god of rain and thunder. The harappans are well aware of the seasonal rainfall and flooding and drainage system. They have a good knowledge and understanding about water management and conservation of natural resources. They pioneered the urban sanitation system, boasting complex sewage system and drainage connection, cities like Mahajo-Daro features soak-pits, outdoor latrines, cesspools, and drainage channels showcasing early waste water treatment efforts. The use of terracotta pipes for waste water disposal demonstrates an early attempt at treatment. Mohanjo-Daro, the largest city belonging to Harappa culture had over 700 open wells.¹ Ancient Bhartiya cities like Kalibangan and Bonawali exhibited sewage systems showcasing variations in waste water collection methods. The Harappan Great Bath and the Dholavira reservoir system exemplify advanced hydraulic engineering. In Dholavira the artificial ponds are best

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example for water conservation. The people of Dholavira take water from the two seasonal rivers namely Mansar and Manhar for use of extra water level in rivers during rainy seasons the people make dam and divert the water in wells and ponds through canals. Lothal is also popular for its water management. The water management of lothal is known as "terrakkal culture". They have canals for irrigation and water purifying plants for drinking water. The Indus Valley civilization exemplifies advanced waterworks and sewerage system both consolidated and distributed concepts.

This ancient and rich civilization advocated the conservation of every type of water in the universe, with a special attention on preserving the river water. Rivers, which are very crucial for irrigating agricultural fields, were deemed vital for the survival of all the living beings. The flowing water of river is considered to be very pure without any pollution. The seven rivers namely mentioned in the Atharvaveda are Sindhu, Vyas (Vipasha), Satluj (Shatudri), Jhelum (Vitasta), Chenab (Assikki), Saraswati and Ravi. These rivers have been given respect like mother in Rigveda.

*ता अस्मश्यं पमसा पित्वमाना शिवादेवीरशिवद् ।
भवन्त सर्वा नद्यः अशिमिहा भवन्तु १*

Rivers satisfy all living beings by providing water, by providing food etc. to them. Rivers love vegetation and they contribute in pleasure of others.

Rigveda laid emphasis on water conservation and it is said in Rigveda that water is like our mother water make us powerful and excellent as ghee make us. Such water needs to be protected in whatever form it is present and where ever it is present.

आपो अस्मान्मातरः शुन्ध्यन्तु घृतेन ना धृत्पवः पुनन्तु १

In Rigveda it is mentioned that 'O humans, you should consume water which is like honeydew and which has medicinal properties like them who consume it in correct way. Always be ready to praise water.'

अप्स्वडन्तरमृतमप्सु भेषजमपामुत प्रशस्तये देवा भक्त वाजिनः १

In the Atharvaveda it is mentioned that you should become energetic and powerful by using such nutritious water.

*अपामहं दिव्यानामपां स्रोतस्यानाम्
रूपामहं प्रणजेनेदश्वा भवय वाजिनः १*

The ancient texts of Rigveda extensively addresses importance of the water cycle and its related processes. It describes how the sun, strategically placed by the divine, illuminates the universe, extracting water as vapour, converting it into clouds, and releasing it as rain. Various verses detail the process of water's journey from earth to the atmosphere and then influenced by the sun and wind, the fragmentation of water into small particles, conversion into vapour due to sunlight, and subsequent rainfall.

जाम्यतीतये धनुर्वयोधा अरुहद्वनम् । दृषदं जिह्वयावधीत् । १

Yajurveda provides insights into water management, highlighting the need for the transporting water to the arid regions through wells, canals, and ponds. It advises people to anticipate natural calamities like draught and floods, taking preventive measures accordingly. Atharvaveda emphasises the prosperity derived from using rainwater for agricultural and other uses. Atharvaveda also discusses drought control by effectively using available water sources, emphasizing the utilization of water to mitigate drought severity. Specific verses provides the guidance for managing different kinds of water bodies such as streams, wells and pools, to reduce the fall out of drought and water scarcity. The vedas also

foretold the significance of water conservation for social welfare and the use of rains, wells, ponds and rivers for agriculture and domestic uses.

The vedic seers, in several hymns, invoked water the purifying agent to be gracious with mankind, to purify men like mothers and to remove all physical defilements. They pray, "May the water be pleasant to our taste, be free from diseases, sin and sickness, be the remover of fear of death, be full of divine qualities and be the strength of eternal laws."⁷

The Vedic period saw a shift in understanding water dynamics. The valuable texts of that period recognised that water wasn't lost but transformed within the water cycle. Ancient Bhartiya literature, including Brihat Samhita, Meghamala and others delved into topics like plant water absorption, evaporation, cloud attributes and forecasting rainfall through natural phenomena observation. The vedas contains the highest of wisdom and knowledge extensively highlighting the significance and relevance of water sources its role for all living organisms, water quality and need of its conservation. Out of the five basic elements of nature, called the Panchamahabhuta, earth (prithvi), fire (agni), water (appah), air (vayu) and sky (aakash)

इमानी च पंचमहाभूतानी पृथ्वी वायु आकाश आपो ज्योतिषी ।।⁸

water is seen as the foremost element and one of that spawned the evolution of the universe. There is a risk to human life and a natural balance when there is a change in the proportion of these five elements in the environment.

Ancient Indians demonstrated advanced knowledge of all aspects of water sources and resources from the vedic to the Mauryan times. They very well understood cloud developments, prediction of rainfall, groundwater structures and water quality, showcasing expertise comparable to the modern science. Jain and Buddhist literature, along with texts like Charaka Samhita provide additional citations to water quality emphasising the importance of preserving forests and soil water. The Mauryan Empire (322-185 BC) widely accepted as the first "hydraulic civilization" had a comprehensive understanding of hydraulic science, on the basis of which were constructed dams, reservoirs, channels with spillways and more.

The Satvahnas introduced the brick and ring wells. Lake and well irrigation was developed on a large scale during the time of Pandaya, Chera and Chola Dynasty. In South India large structures were built across Cauvery and Vaigai rivers. Water resources development on a large scale took place during the Gupta era. The Rajput Dynasty promoted irrigation works in northern India. The 647 sq. km. Bhopal lake was built under king Bhoja. Rajtarangini of Kalhana gives a detail account of irrigation systems developed in the 12th century in Kashmir.

Water conservation is a practice needed for survival. In India various technologies are used to save water which are practical and climatic responsive from the age of Indus Valley civilization, till today many practices are seen in different parts of India. Indians continue to build structures to catch and store the monsoon rains. Water conservation is a process that includes policies, strategies and techniques to sustainably manage natural source of water, protect the hydrosphere, and meet the current and future demand of water. Some of the techniques used to conserve water are :-

A) *Jhalara* : They are typical rectangular shaped step-wells having tiered steps on 3 or all sides which collect the sub-terranean seepage of a stream on reservoir. They ensure an easy and regular supply of water for religious rites, community use, and royal ceremonies. They are human made tanks mostly found in Rajasthan and Gujrat.

- B) *Bawari* : These unique water storage structures once were a part of an ancient network of water storage. The rain water collected was diverted to tanks through canals built on the out skirts of city to supply water.
- C) *Paar system* : This is common water harvesting system practiced in western part of Rajasthan. From a common place rain water flows from the agar (catchment) and percolates into the sandy soil. This is seen in Jaisalmer district.
- D) *Taanka* : This traditional rainwater harvesting is seen in the Thar desert region of Rajasthan. This cylindrically paved underground pit is used to store rainwater from roof tops, courtyards, and artificially prepared catchment flow.
- E) *Zing* : Glacier are found in the cold regions of Ladakh. A part of the land is dug to construct tanks that help to store water from melting glacier. This is a fresh water source that is channelized to the tank with the help of a network of guiding channels.
- F) *Eri* : It is an old water management system used in India to control floods, prevents soil erosion and stop runoff during heavy rainfall in states like Tamil Nadu, these are mostly seen.
- G) *Bandhi/Talab* : Talabs are medium sized reservoirs. There are either natural or manmade structure which were used to store water for household consumption and drinking purposes. The largest man-made Talab in India is the lake Hira Kund in Odissa built on Mahanadi.
- H) *Kund* : According to pages of history, Raja Sur Singh was believed to have built the earliest known kunds, in the village of VadiKa Melan. A kund was a saucer shaped catchment area that has a gentle slope towards the central circular underground well. It was designed to harvest rain water for drinking.
- I) *Johads* : A naturally occurring 3 sided high elevated regions were excavated for building an earthen storage pit called Johads and were oldest systems that were built to conserve and recharge groundwater.
- J) *Baoli* : Baoli was another step well structure, beautifully created into arches, carved motifs and at some places, rooms on either side. A Baoli represent different significance, based on the location it was built. This structure was open for the free drawing of water by people of any religion or caste.

After going through above article it is clear that water is base for our life. Our existence totally depends upon the water. Water is essential for the survival of all forms of life on the earth. If we are not focusing on the proper management of water and its conservation then our next generation will face too much challenges for the water. So the proper management of the water is required. We should pay a concern to its conservation and good management.

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